

ANALYSIS OF ADVERTISING ACTIVITY OF "ISTIQLOL" HOTEL

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Abstract. *This scientific article is devoted to the analysis of advertising activities of "Istiqlol" hotel. The purpose of the research is to study the advertising strategies of the hotel, the advertising channels used and their effectiveness. The article analyzes the modern approaches used in the advertising activities of "Istiqlol" hotel, including digital marketing tools, social media platforms and traditional advertising methods.*

Keywords: *"Istiqlol" hotel, advertising activity, digital marketing, social media marketing, hotel sector, brand image, marketing strategies, tourism of Uzbekistan.*

Introduction. Tourism management is one of the main directions of state policy by the head of our country. The activities in order to observe favorable conditions for the tourism industry, to further improve the documents governing the tourism activities of road entities and the regulatory legal framework, to eliminate all obstacles in the development of tourism, visa and registration procedures, and simple customs control, optimization of the mechanism of regulation of the tourism sector by the state in a passport and specific manner, implementation of measures for the development of the population in the market promotion of tourism entrepreneurial activity and tourism development services, as a result, to obtain statistical information implement measures are marked.

Marketing professional shows how to overcome the problem of complete and comprehensive study of consumer demand, increase demand and sales volume, spread the profitability of market activity, and produce production. A set of marketing communications can help serve that.

The environment in which the tourist (organization) company operates in a complex advertising system. The company provides its services, banks, insurance companies, tourist services production with various services.

These connections have different direction and dynamic character. The tourist firm (problem) must solve the problem of control of the recommended products.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been involved in the development of research on country's investment attractiveness for enterprises and their practical application, including L.P. Kurakov, M.V. Ignatev, A.V. Timiryasova, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall, Byvalsev, A.D. Fedotov, V.M. Kogotkova, Mekhtieva A.YU. We can identify famous scientists such as Giovanna Naranjo, Eugenio Pellic, Víctor Yepes. In our country, a number of marketing researches are carried out, and it is also important to reach scientists who contribute to the development of economic marketing theory based on national characteristics. These include I. Usmanov, I. Tukhliev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, M. Alieva, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others.

Advertising can be viewed from the information process. Personal and non-personal contacts can be made with individuals. Person-to-person communication is between two or more persons who communicate directly with each other through any means of communication (for example, telephone, Internet, and communication). Impersonal communication is the process of non-personal communication between employees.

Research methodology. System, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selection cleaning tools in the research process.

Analysis and results. The role of advertising is to ensure that the organization operates in accordance with organization's interaction with the environment and the internal environment, and must operate in a coordinated manner. The importance of advertising communications of a tourist (enterprise) organization is shown below:

- information load and its source;
- by influencing the market;
- as a tool to control marketing activities.

Effective communication is defined by the fact that the given information is understood in accordance with its first meaning. It can operate as a system that includes four main parts:

- as a contact person sending information;
- information received;
- the information itself;
- receives communication, as a communication system carrying a communication object.

The top result includes the result at the reached address. It may include: changes in address knowledge; support for the action of the addressee itself. Feedback is the addressee's reaction to the communicator's message. It can be seen that a travel firm with a significant account in the feedback marketing system can target.

So, the marketing communication complex is a system of systems, which helps to establish and maintain mutual relations between the contact destination and the tourism organization.

Targeted communication programs. Let's take a closer look at the targeted support of marketing communications of tourism firms. Who lost marketing communications? Of course, to all organizations, firms and individuals participating in the tourist markets with the activities of their travel agencies.

The study of hotel structure is important for the study of relationships among the workforce because vertical relationships reflect the level of interaction between employees. As we can see in "ISTIQLOL" hotel, the main figure is the manager responsible for hotel's production activities. At the same time, junior employees show direct involvement of the director, as many management functions remain without authority.

There are five basic operations in manager's job, no matter what activity they are involved in the hospitality industry. The manager, first of all, sets goals, defines specific tasks in each group of goals, makes them effective by communicating them to other employees of the hotel enterprise, whose work is necessary to achieve these goals;

Second, the manager performs an organizational function by analyzing activities and making decisions necessary to achieve goals. He groups problems into an organizational structure and selects employees to solve them;

Thirdly, the manager maintains constant communication within the team, not forgetting the methods of motivation;

The fourth function performed by the manager is to analyze, evaluate and interpret the work results of each employee of the enterprise;

Fifth, it helps people, including their own professional growth.

Due to the interaction of the above components, the manager has the opportunity to make the operation of any enterprise in the hotel sector and the hospitality industry as a whole efficient and profitable.

Thus, the responsibility for making general management decisions is assigned to the highest level of management. Departments are functional units, each of them uses its own technology, but together they have one common goal - to meet the needs of customers.

Units can be routed:

- for the production of services (maid service or restaurant);
- for information services (booking service).

Unfortunately, the development of management functions at "ISTIQLOL" hotel is at an early stage. The service consists of one or two employees, and the restaurant cannot provide the necessary food preparation for the modern conditions of international tourism.

In addition, insufficient development of communication with tourism and excursion companies in "ISTIQLOL" hotel affects the guest reservation system.

Recruitment of seasonal employees is typical for all hotels in non-tourist regions of Uzbekistan. This is related to the seasonality of tourism in Uzbekistan. The peak tourist season is April, May, June and September (partially October). High temperatures in summer and lack of tourism resources in winter make inbound tourism unattractive.

The number and specialization of seasonal employees depends on the needs of the hotel, the composition of guests, as well as factors of the external tourism environment.

The location of "ISTIQLOL" hotel focuses on the following sources of attracting guests:

- Location on the international highway connecting the southern regions of the republic with the central and eastern regions;
- availability of a sanatorium and aquatoria at the location of the hotel;
- natural recreation resources, that is, the availability of recreation zones for weekends.

In Kashkadarya and neighboring Surkhandarya regions, archaeological and historical tourism is attractive for foreign tourists, and health tourism is attractive for local residents. The national music festival "Maqom" held in Shahrisabz, the national folk-art festival held in Surkhandarya is an important source of foreign visitors.

These factors ensure the presence of customers for ISTIQLOL hotel. After the 2020 pandemic, comprehensive measures are being implemented to develop tourism in Uzbekistan. The state program "Travel across Uzbekistan" is particularly effective. This ensures the flow of citizens of Uzbekistan.

The dynamics of guest reception in recent years can be observed from the table below.

As can be seen from the table, the majority of guests in 2023 were citizens of Uzbekistan - 2,043 people, followed by citizens of the CIS - 959 people. Tourists from foreign countries are in third place - 775 people. The number of hotel stays was 6,556, so each tourist has an average of 1.73 overnight stays.

It should be noted that the number of visitors in 2023 has slightly deteriorated. So, in 2022, 4,144 guests were received, and in 2023, this figure was 3,777 guests, or 91 percent compared to the

previous year. Because after the opening of roads and borders in 2022, the number of domestic and foreign tourists has increased dramatically.

Table-1.

Reception indicators of "ISTIQLOL" hotel guests for 2022-2023.

No.	months	Tourists served				Number of nights
		Total	Including			
			Far abroad	CIS	Uzbekistan	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	2021 year	4144	1001	1371	1772	9362
1	January	195	26	57	112	370
2	February	136	14	22	100	218
3	March	240	58	84	98	492
4	April	170	45	38	87	357
5	May	361	129	147	85	650
6	june	469	73	201	195	1078
7	july	259	45	30	184	440
8	August	910	288	428	194	2639
9	September	596	190	264	142	1609
10	October	344	57	52	235	757
11	november	283	32	37	214	453
12	December	181	44	11	126	299
	2022	3777	775	959	2043	6556
1	January	217	24	47	146	304
2	February	246	51	89	106	320
3	March	276	68	96	112	497
4	April	324	35	118	171	680
5	May	634	166	165	303	1141
6	june	361	78	104	179	578
7	july	313	42	65	206	563
8	August	314	77	87	150	534
9	September	344	116	94	134	826
10	October	153	38	45	70	321
11	november	343	24	25	294	515
12	December	252	56	24	172	277

A characteristic feature of "ISTIQLOL" hotel is that in 2023, a significant share of visitors will be tourists from foreign countries (21 percent) and CIS countries (25 percent).

Customer service is the main activity and main source of income of ISTIQLOL hotel. The table below shows hotel's average revenue per guest and per night.

As can be seen from the table above, the per capita incomes vary greatly, from 530,000 soums to 1,015,000 soums. The same phenomenon is observed according to the indicator of 1 person-day, that is, the amount of income will be from 268 thousand to 455 thousand soums, we believe that it is the specific characteristics of the marketing activity of this hotel.

Table 2.

Comparative income indicators of "ISTIQLOL" hotel for the months of 2022

No.	months	Population, people	Number of overnight stays, person-days	Amount of income, thousand soums	
				For 1 person	1 per person per day
1	January	195	370	530	280
2	February	136	218	430	268
3	March	240	492	780	380
4	April	170	357	915	435
5	May	361	650	820	455
6	june	469	1078	1035	450
7	july	259	440	645	380
8	August	910	2639	1045	360
9	September	596	1609	1215	450
10	October	344	757	1000	455
11	november	283	453	545	340
12	December	181	299	530	320

Based on the analysis of the customer base for 2023, the following groups of service consumers of ISTIQLOL hotel were identified:

- individual tourists (16.1%);
- entrepreneurs (18.5%);
- city guests (20.8%);
- city visitors for tourism and recreation (15.3%)
- conference and festival participants (29.3%).

The study also found that: the contingent of regular participants used services only once.

Table 3.

Analyzing Hotel Profitability Indicators on «INDEPENDENCE» One thousand soums for 2022-2023.

Indicators	Years		Deviation, (+,-)	Change rate, %
	2021 year	2022		
Income from the sale of goods, products, works, services	1008911	8805830	7796919	8.7 times
Cost of sold goods, products, works, services	811564	6431310	5619746	7.9 times
gross profit	197347	2374510	2177163	12 times
Profit from sale	110049	1026450	916401	9.3 times
Profit before tax	97091	486340	389249	5 times
Net profit	73486	276990	203504	3.7 times

As can be seen from the table, hotel from 2022 to 2023 on "INDEPENDENCE» Worked harmlessly since 2022. There is an increase in all profit indicators until 2023.

For example, sales revenue increased 8.7 times and amounted to 8805.8 million soums. Such an increase in income is due to the increase in the prices of tourism services, inflation and

the composition of hotel customers. Similarly, there was a significant increase in gross profit and net profit. In 2022, the net profit of the hotel amounted to about 277 million soums, which made it possible to modernize the hotel services, including the system for the development of advertising activities.

As mentioned above, hotel "ISTIQLOL" located on a busy highway, determines the types and forms of advertising activity:

A) This applies primarily to outdoor advertising. Outdoor advertising - advertising messages placed on the street, on the exterior surfaces of buildings and vehicles. They can be presented in graphic, video and/or text form. The exterior advertising element for the hotel is the facade of the building.

Outdoor advertising in hotel buildings - "Hotel", "Restaurant" and their names must be repeated in the state language, in Latin or Cyrillic alphabet. In addition to its artistic qualities, advertising aims to distinguish the hotel from other buildings.

It has bright and attractive outdoor advertising, which is immediately noticeable on the road and attracts attention. In addition, the hotel uses a banner on the side of the highway on both sides of the road. In addition to the large sign at the hotel door, there is also a sign in three languages for the convenience of guests.

B) Internal advertisement of "ISTIQLOL" hotel— the atmosphere in the lobby affecting the guests inside the hotel complex. Internal advertising is designed to introduce guests to additional services and useful offers provided by the hotel, and to provide information about hotel's partners. This type of promotion includes information booklets, loyalty cards, hotel club cards, souvenirs with the hotel logo, room and lobby information folders.

C) Outdoor advertising of the hotel, aimed at informing consumers about the hotel services, regardless of the location of potential guests. External advertising includes media advertising, hotel's own website, social media pages, travel portals and branded hotel products.

"ISTIQLOL" hotel uses the following types of outdoor advertising:

Posting information on the republican and regional websites of "Uzbekturizm" Tourism and Sports Development Agency, posting information on the website of hotels and tourism enterprises of Kashkadarya authority using the "Yandex" search system ([https://yandex.uz\)/maps/org/hotel_istiqlal/41500497949/?ll=66.569722%2C38.335804&z=13](https://yandex.uz)/maps/org/hotel_istiqlal/41500497949/?ll=66.569722%2C38.335804&z=13))

Unfortunately, the hotel does not have its own website on the Internet, not even an email address where you can contact the administrator.

Hotel "ISTIQLOL" guarantees the client that the room will be at his disposal until the departure time the next day after arrival. In turn, the customer guarantees payment for the room even if the reservation is not canceled or used according to hotel's cancellation policy.

In addition to mandatory services included in the payment for accommodation, the hotel "ISTIQLOL" can provide additional services to guests for an additional fee.

The following services can be provided to guests at no extra charge: calling an ambulance; using a first aid kit; delivery to correspondence number after receipt; wake up at a certain time; provision of boiling water, needles, thread, one dish and cutlery.

Thus, hotel services are provided to hotel consumers, that is, persons who intend to use hotel services directly for their personal (household) needs and who book and pay for hotel services. The main services of the hotel are accommodation and meals (breakfast), included in the room price and provided to the consumer. Consumers of hotel services use hotel rooms.

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